

MODERN METHODS BY WHICH THE TEACHER ORGANIZES INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Annotation

this article discusses the modern methods by which the teacher organizes innovative activities in primary education.

Keywords

innovation, speech, thinking, educational material, methodology, educational effectiveness, teaching and upbringing, comparison, poetry, double spheres

As the student's knowledge, worldview develops, his speech and thinking also grow steadily.

Fluent, concise, touching speech gives the listener gives pleasure. One of the main tasks of the school is to teach its students to speak like this. The current system of giving science at a high level is aimed at establishing the foundations of science, developing thinking, realizing and imagining the universe in one whole, correctly realizing what is happening around, educating young people who can understand them in essence.

The dispersion of subjects taught in schools creates a one-look worldview in a school graduate. From the application of such modern types of lessons, the main goal is to activate the activities of the audience in the educational process, to achieve a high level of assimilation of educational material.

Such technology teaches students to imagine the world in a special way, makes it possible to connect practice with life, not to memorize theoretical rules literally, to realize the harmony of personality and society, to achieve a color of thoughts, to reflect non-standard, and also to understand ways to develop oneself. To improve the effectiveness of education, programs and textbooks in the state of integration should be created.

The teacher organizes innovative activities and its formation it can define its stages as follows:

The first stage - ready-made methodological recommendations are clearly copied.

The second stage - some new devices (modifications), methods are introduced into the existing system.

The third stage - the content, methods and form of implementation of a new idea will be fully developed.

The fourth stage-the teacher develops his own concept and methodology of teaching and upbringing.

In this process, it is necessary to familiarize yourself with the process of personality growth training, problematic training technology, the use of active educational methodology and innovation. The main content of the first stage is organized by the acquisition of general psychological and pedagogical knowledge, the formation of skills and competencies for the analysis of their activities.

At the second stage of the formation of innovative activities in teachers, the following tasks must be completed:

- creative development of pedagogical activity;
- spiritual-cultural knowledge enhancement;
- formation of the need to master pedagogical innovations;
- development of pedagogical reflectivity;
- formation of an innovative information background as a new type of activity.

In the preparation of their teachers for the performance of these tasks, it is possible to organize problem training, self-awareness trainings, familiarize themselves with the developing technologies of teaching, use personality-oriented technologies of teaching, interpret author's concepts, teach them to choose teaching methods, pedagogical techniques and technology trainings, use independent work.

At the third and fourth stages of the formation of innovative activities, it is necessary to perform the following tasks:

modernization of pedagogical activity and the technology of pedagogical communication in one whole case; mastering the technology of innovative activities.

When preparing teachers for innovative activities, it is necessary to take into account the psychological environment in the team, to what extent the members of the team are aware of the innovations in the world education market. Today's educational process is manifested in the fact that the educator's humanized attitude to the individual is aimed at loving children, grieving for their fate, high confidence in children, the emergence of mutual cooperation, a high level of communication culture, the abandonment of direct coercion of educators, on the contrary, the predominance of positive stimulation, tolerance of shortcomings found in children's activities, the use of

The "double balloons" method. Through this method, topics are strengthened. In this case, any verse of the desired poem will be written in balloons. On balloons made of colored paper, he finds words left falling from the poem.

At present, young people must be strong and able to compete spiritually and educationally. With their knowledge and skills, they must reach the world level and show the strength of our country to the whole world. There is also a lot of talk about supporting the youth of our homeland in every way. Work on the creation of necessary conditions for their acquisition of modern knowledge, maturation as a person of mature spirituality continues consistently. An important guarantee of the rise of the land is considered to be the strong knowledge of the people. Neither a country, relying on its mental strength and capabilities, nor developing spiritual, mental and moral values in human thought, nor raising the national spirit of society, nor rising to the level of great progress. The changes in this regard in our country are admirable.

principles of management of innovational processes:

- a humanitarian principle aimed at meeting the needs of individual, team members.
- the principle of value orientation, reflecting the strategic development of an educational institution;
- the principle of orientation towards prophecy, which assumes taking into account the changing internal and external needs of the educational institution;
- the principle of purposefulness of the development of an educational institution, which generates the interest of the subjects of innovation and the possibility of its implementation;
- the principle of democratization of the pedagogical community, aimed at the free implementation of discussion, development and management decisions in all branches of the internal management of the educational institution;
- coordination of innovative processes, the principle of sustainability orientation of the activities of an educational institution that ensures its development;
- identification of problems in the educational institution, their scope

LIST OF LITERATURE USED:

1. Resolution No. 187"on approval of state educational standards of general secondary education and secondary special, vocational education".